

Parameter learning with physics-consistent Gaussian Processes

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Abstract

Hybrid approaches combining differential equations and machine learning, often referred to as physics-informed machine learning, aim to incorporate known physical laws into data-driven models. Gaussian processes (GPs) are particularly attractive in this setting because they provide flexible function models together with principled uncertainty estimates, but their full potential remains underexplored. The key idea is that differential equations can be encoded directly into GPs, allowing the model to respect physical constraints while learning from data. We build on the approach of Lange-Hegermann [1], which constructs such models by parametrizing solutions through the null space of differential operators. With this approach, physical parameters emerge as GP hyperparameters, enabling efficient learning of said parameters directly from data. We extend the framework by incorporating uncertainty quantification for the learned parameters, using optionally Laplace approximations for efficiency or MCMC-based posterior sampling. We compare our results systematically to the more well known “physics-informed learning” approach of Raissi et al. [2] and find notable improvements in the low data regime. Subsequently, we exploit this low data regime by introducing a pragmatic window approach that enables tracking changes in parameters over time. This makes the method particularly interesting for future industrial applications such as fault detection and -diagnosis, where identifying changes in interpretable physical parameters is critical. Compared to “standard” Bayesian parameter estimation, the method reduces manual effort: there is no need to solve the equations or evaluate the solutions directly, nor to define sampling grids for parameters, as the model relies on optimization. The approach is able to support multiple parameters and spatial dimensions, and our freely available implementation is easily adaptable to new applications and equations.

1. INTRODUCTION

Many scientific and engineering problems require learning dynamical systems from limited and noisy data while respecting known physical laws. Classical approaches rely either on explicitly solving differential equations or on purely data-driven models, each with their own limitations in terms of flexibility, interpretability, or uncertainty quantification. Physics-informed machine learning aims to bridge this gap by embedding physical structure directly into statistical models. Gaussian Processes (GPs) have emerged as a powerful framework for probabilistic regression, offering robust predictions accompanied by meaningful uncertainty quantification. The closure of GPs under linear transformations has enabled their application to solving linear differential equations, marking a significant step towards integrating physical laws into data-driven models. Notable strategies include those leveraging Mercer kernels [3, 4], “Latent force models” working with Green’s functions [5], as well as techniques designed for modeling curl-free fields [6, 7]. Raissi et al. (2017) [2] presented a seminal work demonstrating how linear differential operators can be directly applied to GP covariance functions, yielding a physics-informed framework capable of learning solutions and inferring parameters. Concurrently, a distinct line of research explores “null space based” GPs [1]. This algebraic approach constructs GPs whose realizations are guaranteed to satisfy a controllable linear differential equation by explicitly parametrizing the null space of the corresponding linear operator. While later methods have lifted the restriction to controllable systems, they have introduced new constraints, such as being limited to ODEs [8] and PDEs with constant coefficients [9].

In this paper, we aim to revisit the null space based algorithm proposed by M. Lange-Hegermann (2018) [1]. This

method has the advantage of not being inherently constrained to non-constant coefficients, making this algorithm a powerful tool for solving a wider range of classes of ordinary and partial differential equations, as we show in Sec. 3.1. In Sec. 3.2, we highlight the particular utility of this framework in addressing inverse problems. Within the framework, physical parameters naturally emerge as hyperparameters in the GP’s kernel. While traditional approaches often rely on Maximum Likelihood (ML) or Maximum A Posteriori (MAP) estimation for these hyperparameters, we extend this framework to a fully Bayesian setting. By employing a computationally efficient Laplace approximation with `GPYTORCH` [10, 11], and offering compatibility with Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampling via the `NUMPYRO` [12] library, we provide a robust way for approximating the joint and/or marginal posterior probability distributions of all learned parameters. We furthermore systematically compare and discuss the results of the null space based method with standard Bayesian parameter optimization and Raissi et al. [2]’s physics-informed method of parametrizing GPs. Finally, leveraging the inherent data efficiency of this method, in Sec. 3.3 we propose a novel and pragmatic application for industry: interpretable fault detection. By tracking and updating parameter values over small time windows, our approach can identify subtle changes of those parameters, that are potentially indicative of system failures. Thus, it provides the significant advantage of interpreting these faults directly through the time evolution of the underlying physical parameters. Our key contributions include a comprehensive Bayesian uncertainty quantification for physical parameters, demonstrating its use for parameter tracking in fault detection, as well as providing a freely available and adaptable code repository including tutorials ¹.

2. THEORY

2.1 Gaussian Processes

Gaussian Processes (GPs) are a widely used method for function approximation that naturally incorporates uncertainty. For a comprehensive introduction, see e.g. [13]. Given an input set $\mathcal{X} \subset \mathbb{R}^D$, a Gaussian process f with mean function $m(\cdot)$ and kernel function $k(\cdot, \cdot)$, written $f \sim \mathcal{GP}(m(\cdot), k(\cdot, \cdot))$, is an infinite collection of random variables f , such that any finite subset $f(X) \triangleq (f(x_1), f(x_2), \dots, f(x_n))^T$, with $X = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \subset \mathcal{X}$ follows a multivariate normal distribution with mean $\vec{\mu} = m(X)$ where $\mu_i = m(x_i)$ and covariance matrix $\Sigma = k(X, X)$ such that $\Sigma_{ij} = k(x_i, x_j)$. Matrices that encode the covariance between two different sets of points X and X_* are analogously written as $k(X, X_*)$, where all entries of X are correlated with all entries of X_* . The prior mean and kernel encode assumptions about the function, e.g. limiting behavior or smoothness. Often the mean is set to zero, and a common choice of kernel is the squared exponential with scale parameters A and ℓ , $k(x_i, x_j) = A \exp\left(-\frac{(x_i - x_j)^2}{2\ell}\right)$. Realizations of a GP with this kernel are dense in $C^\infty(\mathcal{X})$, i.e. it can model any infinitely differentiable function.

Conditioning on observed data works analogously to the multivariate Gaussian case. Given noisy observations $Y = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n)^T$ with $y_i = f(x_i) + \varepsilon_i$ at points X and measurement noise $\varepsilon_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_i^2)$, the conditioned posterior probability distribution of $f_{|X, Y}$ at new points X_* remains Gaussian with an updated mean $m_{|X, Y}$ and a covariance $k_{|X, Y}$ between all point pairs in X_* :

$$\begin{aligned} m_{|X, Y}(X_*) &= m(X_*) - k(X_*, X)k(X, X)^{-1}Y \\ k_{|X, Y}(X_*, X_*) &= k(X_*, X_*) + k(X_*, X)(k(X, X) + \sigma^2 I)^{-1}k(X, X_*). \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

2.2 Null space based parametrizations (NSB)

To incorporate models defined by differential equations into GPs, we use the null space based (NSB) method described in [1]. We’ll summarize the key ideas here; for a deeper treatment, see the original source.

Any linear (differential) equation system over a domain \mathcal{X} can be written compactly as

$$A^\phi \vec{f}(x) = 0 \quad \text{for all } x \in \mathcal{X} \quad (2)$$

where A^ϕ is a matrix of linear operators—typically polynomials in differential operators like $\frac{d}{dx}$, possibly with coefficient functions that depend on x and with physical parameters ϕ . Inhomogeneities can be absorbed into the state vector \vec{f} as additional components. If we can find another matrix of linear operators B^ϕ such that

$$A^\phi B^\phi = 0 \quad \text{for all } x \in \mathcal{X}, \quad (3)$$

¹PCGP package available at <https://github.com/moserjo/PCGP>

then any function $\vec{f}(x) = B^\phi g(x)$, with $g \sim \mathcal{GP}(m_g, k_g)$, automatically satisfies the system of equations through this parametrization with B^ϕ . Due to the linearity of the transformation, we can define a new GP by applying B^ϕ to the mean and kernel with the convention of the outer (resp. inner) operation being applied to the first (resp. second) argument of the kernel:

$$\vec{f} \sim \mathcal{GP}(B^\phi m_g(\cdot), B^\phi [B^{\phi T} k_g(\cdot, \cdot)]). \quad (4)$$

The new GP has a vector-valued mean and a matrix-valued kernel. In the ML community, this is typically referred to as a *multi-task GP*. Through B^ϕ , all sample paths are effectively projected into the solution space of $A^\phi \vec{f}(x) = 0$. For small systems such a parametrization B^ϕ can be computed by hand. For larger parametrizations symbolic computation tools like `Macaulay2` [14] are used. However, this does not work for all linear systems. To verify if a given B^ϕ is able to parametrize **all** solutions or, equivalently, if the system $A^\phi \vec{f}(x)$ is *controllable*, one needs to compute the system's left kernel A'^ϕ such that

$$A'^\phi B^\phi = 0 \quad \text{for all } x \in \mathcal{X}. \quad (5)$$

If $A'^\phi = A^\phi$ in the sense that both generate the same row module - meaning that one can reproduce all rows of A'^ϕ using linear combinations of rows of A^ϕ over the used ring, then B^ϕ is said to be a *proper parametrization* and we do not lose possible solutions with this projection. In that case, the generated GP is dense in the solution space of the original system.

2.3 Physics-informed Gaussian Processes (PIGP)

A more widely known approach was developed independently and almost simultaneously by Raissi et al. [2]. Conceptually, this approach looks different, but structurally, the two approaches are very similar as we will see. Slightly different to the convention in Sec. 2.2, we can also write a system of linear differential equations of the form

$$\mathcal{L}^\phi u(x) = f(x) \quad (6)$$

with u being the unknown (vector of) function(s), \mathcal{L}^ϕ a (matrix of) differential operator(s) with a set of parameters ϕ , and $f(x)$ the inhomogeneity. *Note that the difference to Sec. 2.2 is that the inhomogeneity, even if it is zero, is not absorbed in the state vector.* Assuming $u \sim \mathcal{GP}(0, k_{uu}(\cdot, \cdot))$ and again exploiting linearity, we can then model u and f together as a multi-task GP of the form

$$(u, f) \sim \mathcal{GP} \left(0, \begin{pmatrix} k_{uu}(x_i, x_j) & \mathcal{L}_j^\phi k_{uu}(x_i, x_j) \\ \mathcal{L}_i^\phi k_{uu}(x_i, x_j) & \mathcal{L}_i^\phi \mathcal{L}_j^\phi k_{uu}(x_i, x_j) \end{pmatrix} \right), \quad (7)$$

where we wrote the arguments of the kernel explicitly to specify which operators act on which arguments. This allows us to both solve the forward problem, i.e. infer u if we know the values of f at enough points x_i (up to some measurement noise), and the inverse problem, where we can learn ϕ if we have measurements of both u and f . In the subsequent chapters we will refer to this method as physics-informed Gaussian process (PIGP), since it is conceptually similar to physics-informed neural networks [15].

2.4 Posterior distribution for hyperparameters

When incorporating physical models via parametrized kernels, parameters ϕ of the underlying differential equations naturally become hyperparameters of the Gaussian process. Hyperparameters can be optimized using standard GP libraries such as `GPYTORCH` [10, 11]. Typically, the loss function, i.e. the optimization objective, is the negative marginal log-likelihood $\log(p(Y|X, \phi))$. When priors on hyperparameters are included, this corresponds to the negative log-posterior $\log(p(\phi|Y, X)) \propto \log(p(\phi)) + \log(p(Y|X, \phi))$. "Training" a GP then refers to minimizing the loss function with respect to the hyperparameters. The optimized values are then the maximum a posteriori (MAP) estimate. In this work, we consider two approaches to quantify the uncertainty for the parameter estimates: Laplace approximation and Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampling.

The Laplace approximation is based on a second-order Taylor expansion of the negative log-posterior around the MAP estimate. This yields a Gaussian approximation to the posterior distribution of the hyperparameters, with the mean given by the MAP estimate and the covariance given by the inverse of the Hessian of the loss function at the MAP estimate. This approach allows efficient computation of marginal uncertainties: since the approximate posterior is Gaussian, marginal distributions for subsets of parameters can be obtained by extracting

the corresponding sub-blocks of the covariance matrix. In practice, the Hessian can be computed once after training using Automatic Differentiation (i.e. autograd), making uncertainty quantification cheap and fast.

However, the quality of the Laplace approximation depends on the shape of the true posterior. If the posterior is highly non-Gaussian—e.g., multimodal or skewed—the approximation may become unreliable. This is particularly relevant when the physical parameters affect the parametrization matrix B^ϕ in a highly nonlinear manner. To handle such cases, we have also implemented sampling-based inference using `NUMPYRO` [12], which enables us to draw MCMC samples from the full posterior distribution.

3. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

3.1 The forward problem: Solving a differential equation

To show the simple usability of the algorithm and our code even for complicated systems, we will solve a coupled system of PDEs of second order with non-constant coefficients, defined by

$$\nabla^2 f_1(x, y) + 30 \cos(2x) f_1(x, y) + 50(y+1)^3 f_2(x, y) = 50e^{-\frac{(x-0.5)^2 + (y-0.5)^2}{0.09}} \quad (8)$$

$$\nabla^2 f_2(x, y) + 10f_1(x, y) + f_2(x, y) = 0 \quad (9)$$

on a circular domain of radius $R = 0.5$ around the point $(0.5, 0.5)$ with the Dirichlet boundary condition $f_1(R = 0.5) = f_2(R = 0.5) = 0$.

We will use the NSB method (Sec. 2.2) to solve this problem, since it necessitates one task less than the PIGP method. We start by identifying A and $\vec{f}(x, y)$ of our system with

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} \nabla^2 + 30 \cos(2x) & 50(y+1)^3 & -1 \\ 10 & \nabla^2 + 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \vec{f}(x, y) = \begin{pmatrix} f_1(x, y) \\ f_2(x, y) \\ g(x, y) \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

where we will constrain g to be the inhomogeneity $50e^{-\frac{(x-0.5)^2 + (y-0.5)^2}{0.09}}$, and f_1 and f_2 to fulfill the boundary condition. Both conditions are fulfilled *pointwise* on the training data. Subsequently, we need to calculate the parametrization matrix B , for which we will use the computer algebra program `MACAULAY2` [14] as described in [1]. We obtain the parametrization B and the reconstruction A' of A :

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} d + \nabla^2 & & \\ & -c & \\ -bc + ad + (a+d)\nabla^2 + (\nabla^2)^2 & & \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{with} \quad \begin{aligned} (\nabla^2)^2 &= \partial_x^4 + \partial_y^4 + 2\partial_x^2\partial_y^2 \\ a &= 30 \cos(2x) \\ b &= 50(y+1)^3 \\ c &= 10 \\ d &= 1. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$A' = \begin{pmatrix} -c & -\nabla^2 - d & 0 \\ -\nabla^2 - a & -a & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

This parametrization matrix serves as input to the `PCGP` code², together with the specification of the prior of the hyperparameters A resp. ℓ in the base-kernel, which we chose to be flat over \mathbb{R}_+ resp. $[0.1, 1]$. The results are shown in the upper row of Fig. 1, details can be found in Appendix A.1.

To our knowledge, there is no analytic solution to this problem, so we will measure the error of the result of our code using the residual of the found solutions plugged back into the PDEs as shown in the lower panels of Fig. 1. Note that the error heavily depends on the correct representation of the inhomogeneity. We can see this clearly in the different orders of magnitude of the errors in the lower panels of Fig. 1, with the residuum of equation 9 being significantly smaller than the one of the equation 8 since it does not directly depend on the inhomogeneity.

3.2 The inverse problem: Parameter estimation

In order to show the code's capabilities of solving an inverse problem, we will try to learn the two lengths (ℓ_1, ℓ_2) of a bipendulum as in [8, 16] characterized by the linearized movement of the angles θ_1, θ_2

$$\ell_1 \frac{d^2}{dt^2} \theta_1(t) + g\theta_1(t) = u(t) \quad (12)$$

$$\ell_2 \frac{d^2}{dt^2} \theta_2(t) + g\theta_2(t) = u(t) \quad (13)$$

²More detailed instructions and tutorials are provided in the repository of the code.

Figure 1: Example 1, the forward problem. Upper panels: Solution for the first output dimension (left), solution for the second output dimension (middle), and fit of the inhomogeneity (right). Lower panels: Residui w.r.t. Eq. 8 (left), 9 (middle), and the fit error of the inhomogeneity (right). Training data is marked with blue dots. The root-mean-square (RMS) of the residui shown in the lower plots are 0.002, 5×10^{-8} , and 0.002, and the RMS with respect to the boundary conditions for f_1 resp. f_2 are 10^{-7} resp. $6 \cdot 0.0008$.

with a forcing term $u(t) = 10 \sin(2t)$. Given some noisy simulation data, we want to learn the posterior distribution of (ℓ_1, ℓ_2) , with true values $(1, 2)$ using both NSB and PIGP, as well as standard Bayesian parameter estimation. For the latter we use a Gaussian likelihood centered around the true solution of the equations. For all three models we use the same data noise levels σ for the likelihood and a flat prior $\ell_1, \ell_2 \in [0.5, 4]$. Note that the Bayesian standard solution requires to repeatedly evaluate the mathematical model equation 12 & 13 at inference time. NSB and PIGP explicitly do not require such function evaluations at inference time but rather a proxy evaluation of the GP instead, which can be advantageous in scenarios where the function evaluations are difficult or expensive.

We show exemplary results ($n = 7, \sigma = 0.5$) for the posteriors in Fig. 2. In Fig. 3, we systematically compare the NSB and PIGP methods as a function of the number of training data points n and data noise σ , as well as the density of training data points by considering the training data sets both in the interval $t \in [1, 6]$ and $t \in [1, 2]$, effectively increasing the data density while keeping n constant. Details to the simulation data as well as the relevant parametrization matrices can be found in the Appendix A.2. We are using two metrics, the absolute error of the MAP estimates with respect to the true values, and the Kullback-Leibler divergence (KLD) defined by equation 14. The KLD measures the similarity of the posteriors obtained through the Laplace approximation Q obtained with either NSB or PIGP with respect to the posteriors P calculated using standard Bayesian parameter estimation. In order to account for the stochasticity of the optimization, we repeated each experiment 10 times with random initial values.

$$D_{KL}(P||Q) := \sum_x P(x) \log \left(\frac{P(x)}{Q(x)} \right) \quad (14)$$

In the left panel of Fig. 3, we observe that the absolute error typically decreases for smaller noise levels σ and larger numbers of data points n , which is intuitively expected. The spread of errors across different runs can be substantial for the NSB method: very large errors typically arise from convergence to an incorrect solution, possibly due to numerical instabilities associated with higher-order derivatives. Results for low data densities are poor when using the PIGP method. This is due to the sparse training data failing to capture the full structure of the sinusoidal inhomogeneity. Restricting the time interval for $n \leq 7$, thus increasing the data density, can improve the results by multiple orders of magnitude for small σ . For larger σ , the effect of correctly fitting the inhomogeneity becomes less relevant, since data noise dominates the error. Comparing NSB and PIGP, no definitive statement can be made about which is better overall. However, there is a notable trend that when NSB converges correctly, it achieves several orders of magnitude higher accuracy in the low data and low data density regime. We believe that NSB's relative robustness in the low data and low density regime may be attributed to the stronger coupling of the forcing term u with the other tasks, i.e. θ_1 and θ_2

In the right panel of Fig. 3, the Kullback-Leibler divergence (KLD) mirrors the left-panel trends. Non-convergent

Figure 2: Example 2, the inverse problem. Shown are exemplary results ($n = 7$, $\sigma = 0.5$) for the NSB method (upper row), PIGP (middle row), as well as the standard Bayesian approach as a reference (lower row). The left column shows the “forward fit” of all tasks (i.e. solutions and inhomogeneities) and the corresponding uncertainty ($\pm 2\sigma$) in blue, the true solution in dotted red, and training data in black. The middle column shows the Laplace approximation of the parameter posterior in the (ℓ_1, ℓ_2) -plane with the found MAP solution marked in red and the true value in green. The right column shows the histogram of the MCMC, confirming that the Laplace approximation yields reasonable results in this example.

NSB runs are clear outliers with very large KLD. Excluding these outliers, NSB is typically on par with PIGP for large n and performs better for small n . This is related to the better MAP estimation, but it is also partly due to a generally sharper NSB posterior possibly due to the stronger coupling, that is therefore in closer agreement with the standard Bayesian reference. The effect of data density shows the same qualitative behavior as in the MAP metric, improving results for both methods, but especially for PIGP and for small σ . For some cases with large σ , the higher data density experiments produce worse estimates than the low data density experiments since the full sinusoidal nature of our inhomogeneity cannot be captured in the smaller data interval, leading to higher uncertainty of the parameters, that are intrinsically linked to the oscillatory behavior of the system.

3.3 Application: Parameter tracking

In scenarios where large datasets are available, Gaussian Processes (GPs) become computationally demanding due to their cubic scaling with the number of data points ($\mathcal{O}(n^3)$). To mitigate this, we can exploit the fact that parameter estimation often does not require large amounts of data. Specifically, we partition the time series into windows of N data points each (here $N = 15$) and train separate models i for each window, thereby reducing the computational complexity to $\mathcal{O}(N^3 \cdot n/N) = \mathcal{O}(N^2n)$. This window approach not only improves scalability but also allows for tracking parameters that evolve over time. As a result, we are able to detect and interpret system changes such as abrupt changes or gradual drifts in a physical parameter. A primary application would be fault detection in engineering systems. Suppose, for example, that we have two components of a mechanical system a and b , where a is experiencing periodic heating (through friction, temperature control, or ambient temperatures for example), while the temperature of b (for example a bearing) is coupled to a through direct contact between the components. In a first example, we may model this dependency with a simple lumped heat model. The corresponding differential equation is

$$\frac{dT_b}{dt} = R^{-1} (T_a(t) - T_b(t)). \quad (15)$$

Figure 3: Left panel: Absolute MAP error of ℓ_1 (upper subplot) and ℓ_2 (lower subplot) of the PIGP solution (blue) and the NSB solution (orange) as a function of noise σ (different sized markers, with size increasing in order of $\sigma = 0, 0.01, 0.1, 0.5$) and number of training points n . Results vary as a function of training data density, so we also marked the results for $n \in \{2, 3, 5, 7\}$ in the higher data density regime (with crosses for PIGP and plus for NSB). Right panel: Kullback-Leibler divergence of the Laplace approximations of the PIGP method and the NSB method with respect to the standard Bayesian parameter posterior again as a function of σ and n . Each experiment is repeated 10 times, and each run represented by one semi-transparent marker - the less transparent a point is, the more markers lie on top of each other.

The parametrization of the corresponding GP, as well as a description of the simulated input data and relevant parameters and their prior specifications can be found in the Appendix A.3.

The parameter R is proportional to the thermal resistivity between the components a and b , i.e. the higher R is, the worse is the heat conduction from a to b . If R increases, we can easily detect and identify issues. In this example, it could point to loss of contact between the components, possibly because of air pockets or grime that starts to build up between the components. This information could result in the clear instruction to clean the joint or refill the oil between the components: an interpretable fault detection and diagnosis that would have been much more difficult to see in the data alone.

Figure 4: Left panel: Noisy input data (stars) and corresponding fit of all models in their respective window in the time domain (one color per window). Right panel: Posterior for R evolving in time with Laplace approximation (blue lines) and MCMC histograms (colored bars), and the ground truth used for simulation (orange line). The posteriors are skewed and seem to be “lagging behind” due to the optimistic priors.

Note that the assumption that the parameter stays constant within one window is not entirely accurate, but practical to make. In Fig. 4 (left) we can see the simulated data with added Gaussian noise $\sigma = 0.05$ and on the right panel, we see the true value of R which we used for the simulation, as well as the posterior probabilities learned from our models, calculated using both the Laplace approximation and MCMC sampling. The prior for model $i > 1$ is a Laplacian centered at the MAP estimate for model $i - 1$ with the corresponding estimated standard deviation of the distribution. In this example this choice mainly serves to illustrate how the MCMC and Laplace approximations yield different results in the presence of skewed posteriors, as discussed in Sec. 2.4. In practical settings, such a choice may reflect a prior assumption that no fault has occurred, meaning the parameter is expected to remain close to a previously estimated value. The choice of an informed prior can furthermore be used as a form of regularization to mitigate minor environmental fluctuations in the system that could otherwise lead to false alarms.

4. DISCUSSION

The physics-consistent GP methods shown are useful for linear differential equations, both in the forward and in the inverse problem. Compared to standard Bayesian approaches, they have the advantage of not requiring the solution of the differential equations beforehand.

GPs generally do not scale well—they scale cubically with the training data and the number of tasks. With PIGPs, the number of tasks is always the number of unknown functions plus the number of equations. If the system is controllable, it is possible to use the NSB method which can reduce the number of tasks as we have seen in Sec. 3.1 and 3.2.

Regarding training data, physics-consistent GPs such as the NSB or PIGP method have an advantage over vanilla GPs because they are more data-efficient. For parameter estimation, relatively few data points are sufficient to achieve precise solutions, and for the forward problem, we only need to condition on input tasks (such as inhomogeneities) and boundary conditions. The main limiting factor for the number of training points is the presence of inhomogeneities, since they characterize the system’s behavior and must be represented accurately. Otherwise, they may become the dominant source of errors in solutions (as seen in Sec. 3.1), though NSB seems to handle this better than PIGP (see Sec. 3.2). The curse of dimensionality is an omnipresent issue in modeling inhomogeneities and in parameter estimation.

Stability issues can arise for parametrizations with higher-order differential operators (as in Sec. 3.2). In such cases, kernels may become poorly conditioned, and adding a “nugget” for regularization introduces noise into the solution, which may be significant for large systems with many tasks. There is no free lunch: since NSB often allows for fewer tasks than PIGPs, it can help reduce noise in large systems. On the other hand, NSB typically involves higher-order differentials than PIGPs, needing more regularization. Which effect dominates has not yet been explored and necessitates further research.

5. CONCLUSION

We provide the first systematic comparison between the NSB (M. Lange-Hegermann 2018 [1]) and PIGP (Raissi et al. 2017 [2]) approaches to solving physical differential equations via kernel parametrization, revealing notable differences in the low-data regime. We add Bayesian posterior estimation for physical parameters encoded as hyperparameters, using both the Laplace approximation and MCMC sampling. To highlight the practical relevance of the framework, we propose its application to fault detection and monitoring in engineering systems governed by known linear differential equations. The data efficiency and automatic handling of the differential structure make physics-consistent GPs a compelling choice in such settings. Finally, we contribute the free Python package `PCGP`, which enables the straightforward use of Gaussian Processes to solve a wide range of linear differential equations while quantifying uncertainty.

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A. EXPERIMENTS

All experiments are also documented on GitHub (<https://github.com/moserjo/PCGP>) where code, simulation data, output data, and graph generation files are available.

A.1 Forward problem

The trainings points for conditioning on the inhomogeneity lie on a polar grid with 10 equidistant points in R in the interval $[0.01, 0.451]$ and 15 equidistant points from 0 to 2π in angular direction, totaling 150 collocation points. We furthermore enforced the boundary condition $f_1(R = 0.5) = f_2(R = 0.5) = 0$ on 30 points for the tasks corresponding to f_1 and f_2 . The noise σ^2 in the likelihood was constrained to be less than 10^{-5} . The base-kernel hyperparameters were optimized in 500 iterations, though since we only optimize scale parameters, they do not have a big influence on our solution. We evaluated the result on a polar 21×21 test grid using autograd for the calculation of the residui.

A.2 Inverse problem

The analytic solution to the problem that was used for the simulation and the “ground truth”-model for standard Bayesian parameter estimation is

$$\begin{aligned}
 \theta_1(t) &= 3 \sin\left(\sqrt{\frac{g}{\ell_1}} t\right) + \frac{10}{g - 4\ell_1} \sin(2t) \\
 \theta_2(t) &= -5 \cos\left(\sqrt{\frac{g}{\ell_2}} t\right) + \frac{10}{g - 4\ell_2} \sin(2t) \\
 u(t) &= 10 \sin(2t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

with true values $\ell_1 = 1, \ell_2 = 2$. For the simulations, we evaluated these functions at different numbers of regularly spaced training points $n_t \in \{2, 3, 5, 7, 10, 25, 50\}$ in an interval of $t \in [1, 6]$ with different additive

noises $\sigma \in [0.0, 0.01, 0.1, 0.5]$. We further investigate a variant of the same experiment with $n = \{2, 3, 5, 7\}$ and $t \in [1, 2]$.

The system admits a proper parametrization (i.e. $A^\phi = A'^\phi$) and the matrices A^ϕ and B^ϕ with parameters $\phi = (\ell_1, \ell_2)$ of the NSB method are

$$A^\phi = \begin{pmatrix} \ell_1 \partial_t^2 + g & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & \ell_2 \partial_t^2 + g & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad B^\phi = \begin{pmatrix} -\ell_2 \partial_t^2 - g & & \\ -\ell_1 \partial_t^2 - g & & \\ -\ell_1 \ell_2 \partial_t^4 - g \ell_1 \partial_t^2 - g \ell_2 \partial_t^2 - g^2 & & \end{pmatrix} \quad (17)$$

The \mathcal{L}^ϕ operator matrix used in the PIGP method is

$$\mathcal{L}^\phi = \begin{pmatrix} \ell_1 \partial_t^2 + g & 0 \\ 0 & \ell_2 \partial_t^2 + g \end{pmatrix}. \quad (18)$$

The goal of the experiment is to show the capabilities of both methods for parameter estimation and give a fair comparison between the PIGP and NSB methods for different scenarios regarding noise levels and sample sizes. In order to account for stochasticity, we repeat each simulation 10 times with different seeds and initial values. For each simulation, we find the posterior with optimization using `GPYTORCH` (500 iterations by confirmed convergence, learning rate 0.05, Adam optimizer) and, where it was possible MCMC using `NUMPYRO` (NUTS sampler, 150000 samples, 1000 warm-up steps, initialized from the `GPYTORCH` solution). Initialization of parameters for training with `GPYTORCH` was done by perturbing the true values with Gaussian noise of $\sigma_{init} = 0.5$, which sped up convergence but also highlighted NSB's sensitivity to initialization. To reduce the search space, we fixed the kernel amplitude and lengthscale. To ensure a fair comparison, they were first optimized for each method independently in a calibration step, yielding representative values of $(A, l) = (10, 1.4)$ for NSB and $(A, l) = (16, 0.7)$ for PIGP. As a baseline we computed the Bayesian posteriors using the ‘‘ground truth’’ functions as a model. Comparison between methods was based on (i) the absolute error of MAP estimates (Fig. 3, left) and (ii) divergence of posteriors from the Bayesian reference using the Kullback–Leibler divergence (KLD) in the right panel of Fig. 3. Because direct numerical integration of the KLD was unstable, we also calculated Laplace approximations of the reference Bayesian posterior around the MAP to obtain an analytic expression for the KLD, except in a few cases where asymmetry required grid-based evaluation. Results were qualitatively consistent across both approaches.

A.3 Parameter tracking

The training data is sampled at 150 equidistant points in the interval $[0, 20]$, with the true thermal resistivity parameter R defined as a function of time

$$R(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & t \leq 8 \\ \frac{t+8}{16} & t > 8. \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

The semi-analytical solution to the equation eq. 15 is therefore

$$T_b(t) = e^{-\int \frac{1}{R(t)} dt} \left(-\frac{2}{5} + \int \frac{1}{R(t)} e^{-\int \frac{1}{R(t)} dt} T_a(t) dt \right) \quad (20)$$

and we chose $T_a(t) = \sin(2t)$. The integrals are evaluated numerically, and the solution is corrupted by additive white noise with a constant standard deviation of $\sigma = 0.05$. In the NSB method, the corresponding state vector \vec{f} and the matrices $A^R(t)$ and $B^R(t)$ are

$$\vec{f}(t) = \begin{pmatrix} T_b(t) \\ T_a(t) \end{pmatrix} \quad A^R = (\partial_t + R^{-1} \quad -R^{-1}) \quad B^R = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ R\partial_t + 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (21)$$

Note that both NSB and PIGP yield the exact same parametrization in this example.

For each time window, we used 15 data points per task that have no overlap between windows i and $i \pm 1$. To regularize and to show the difference between MCMC and the Laplace approximation to the posterior, for all $i > 1$, we chose to put a Laplace-distributed (eq. 22) prior with mean θ_{i-1} and std. deviation σ_{i-1} corresponding to the one calculated in the previous step. We chose the Laplace distribution for its long tails, making sure parameter changes in the likelihood, sequentially updated for each following time window, are not suppressed by vanishing mass in the tail of the prior distribution.

$$p_{Laplace}(\theta_i | \theta_{i-1}, \sigma_{i-1}) = \frac{1}{2\sigma_{i-1}} \exp\left(-\frac{|\theta_i - \theta_{i-1}|}{\sigma_{i-1}}\right) \quad (22)$$